

SOFTWARE FOR THE CONVERGENCE OF THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

Olimova Bahora Shuxratovna

Karshi engineering economics institute, independent researcher

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Annotation: In this article, the importance and relevance of creating a large database in the process of convergence of educational services, as well as their theoretical and practical aspects, are highlighted, and opinions are expressed on this topic. Within the framework of the approach based on the economic directions of the knowledge economy, specific theoretical information is given on the formation of competencies for the purpose of training future specialists in the economic direction.

Key words: Secondary education, higher education, school education, convergence, knowledge economy, pedagogical skills, database, convergence process, educational services.

Conceptual design is the starting point in creating a convergence model of the educational system, which allows logical modeling to occur by structuring and organizing physical and logical connections based on data collection, analysis, and organization. Determining the components of a dataset and the relationships between them is a key design challenge. Formed in Fig.1.

Figure 1. Software of educational system convergence

As we can see from the picture, it is confirmed that the creation of an information base model based on research in the educational system in the

educational system is a strong and well-founded method of more accurate coordination in the information subsystem, which depends on the efficiency of the decisions made for the convergence of the social sphere and the economic sphere. possible In this case, marketing information should not be considered as a set of statistical indicators and a set of unrelated operations for their collection and processing, but as a single, well-founded element of social development. necessary. In the creation of such a set of information, criteria for specific decision-making and functional criteria are taken into account.

Risks are assessed through the following factors:

- Natural and man-made hazards.
- Casual user
- Network risks
- Risk by installing the program
- User apathy
- Database risks
- Hazards through signals
- Risks through employees

To conclude, tIn the research, we attach importance to the information supply to obtain the practical results and calculated indicators of the model system solution of the convergence of the educational system. Materials and documents related to the development of the educational structure, improvement of its infrastructure, documents from statistical reports, organizations, and the results of scientific research are used as a basis for obtaining general information.

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